

NEWSLETTER

VOL 4 ISSUE 1

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From the Editor's Desk

Greetings and a warm welcome to the first issue of ISAJ Newsletter for 2019! We take this opportunity to wish you a happy and productive new year 2019. Have a promising and fulfilling new year.

It is our pleasure to inform you that ISAJ will mark its 10th anniversary this year. The editorial team, on behalf of ISAJ, would like to sincerely thank you all for decade-long support and cooperation which has led us to advance ISAJ initiatives to help the Indian scientists and researchers working in Japan.

In this issue, we present two articles dealing with the DEPSOR based bio-sensors and predictive biomarker in PD-1 blockadetherapy. Biosensors are analytical devices, which detect the presence of chemical substances and manufactured by combining biological components with physicochemical detectors. A Biomarker is a measured characteristic which indicates normal biological process or response to any intervention in the human body. This issue also contains a report and photographs of the 9th annual ISAJ symposium held recently.

In the article on predictive biomarker in PD-1 blockade therapy, which has only 40-50% success-rate and requires an indicator, the young scientist briefly explains his efforts in identifying the potentials of mitochondrial activation parameters as a potential biomarker to differentiate between responding and non-responding patients.

Under the section research spotlight of this issue, Dr. Biyani presents his work on sustainable development of Disposable Electrochemical Printed Sensors (DEPSOR)-based biosensors and their analytical platform. The article presents a brief introduction on the developed sensors for testing of heavy metal contamination in drinking water, for on-site enumeration of total viable bacterial count, for early disease information and for the soil fertility test.

ISAJ has successfully organized its 9th annual symposium on 7th Dec 2018 at AIST, Tsukuba. The theme of the symposium was "Interdisciplinary science and technology for safety and quality of life" and the event was attended by about 100 people and it included 16 invited talks and 44 poster-presentations. We present a brief report in the Event Report section of this issue.

We hope you would find the current issue of our Newsletter interesting. We look forward to receiving your feedback, as well as any suggestions/ ideas for improving the newsletter in the future.

In This Issue

- **Research Spotlights**
DEPSOR-based biosensors and analytical platform for the SDGs
- **Event Report**
9th ISAJ Symposium on "Interdisciplinary science and technology for safety and quality of life"
- **Photo Gallery**
9th ISAJ Symposium
- **From the Pen of Young Mind**
Indicators of mitochondrial activation in killer T cells could be a biomarker to predict the PD-1 blockade therapeutic efficacy

News and Notes

Funding and Job opportunities

Science and Engineering Board, India

1. **Visiting Advanced Joint Research Faculty Scheme (VAJRA) (Rolling)**
2. **JC Bose National Fellowship (Rolling)**
3. **Early Career Research (ECR) Award (twice a year: Jan. & Jul)**

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DEPSOR-based biosensors and analytical platform for the SDGs

Dr. Manish Biyani

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Currently, a specially appointed Associate Professor in the School of Material Science, Japan Advanced Institute of Science and Technology. He received a Master of Engineering (2001) and PhD (2004) in Biological Sciences from Saitama University, Japan. He has worked as Research Scientist for three major national projects in Japan: CREATE (2004-2008), CREST (2009-2013) and HLSC (2014-2018). Dr Biyani has been Research Assistant Professor in the Department of Bioengineering at The University of Tokyo from 2009-2013.

During his career, Dr Biyani has built and headed many new startups and platforms for India-Japan collaboration as co-founding director of Biyani Group of Colleges and Biyani BioSolutions Pvt Ltd in Jaipur, India and BioSeeds Corporation in Ishikawa, Japan.

Recently, Dr Biyani has been felicitated by the Japan Foreign Ministry with Commendation award in recognition of his key role in promoting grass-root level people-to-people exchange between Japan and India.

Technological innovation is key to the implementation of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) set by United Nations. We describe a robust and handheld device, called DEPSOR (Disposable Electrochemical Printed Sensor), for the rapid and affordable electrochemical sensing of analytes. The unique combination of hardware (i.e., disposable electrode printed chip and a palm-sized potentiostat), software (i.e., smartphone-supported programming to perform on-site voltammetry analysis) and wetware (i.e., evolutionary molecular engineered bio-probes) elements of high-performance DEPSOR, which are easy to integrate into a diverse applications, make this system extremely portable and affordable with application-ready signal outputs in resource-limited settings.

A series of DEPSOR platform has been developed: DEPSOR-M is for rapid and simultaneous testing of multiple heavy metals in environmental samples including arsenic, cadmium, mercury, lead at ppb levels; DEPSOR-V is for on-site enumeration of total viable bacterial count in milk and other food samples below permissible range set by WHO; DEPSOR-H is for aptamer-based sensing of early disease information for CVD, Cancer, Alzheimer's disease; DEPSOR-N is for farmer-friendly and on-site soil fertility testing [1-3]. With these diverse applications, DEPSOR is highly expected to bring a rapid transformation of electrochemical sensing technologies for mass application and so thus solutions for sustainable development challenges.

References:

- [1] "PEP-on-DEP: A competitive peptide-based disposable electrochemical aptasensor for renin diagnosis," Biosens. Bioelectron., 84, 120, 2016.
- [2] "DEP-On-Go for simultaneous sensing of multiple heavy metals pollutants in environmental samples," Sensors, 17, 45, 2017.
- [3] "Instant enumeration of total viable bacterial counts for food quality assurance using 'DEP-On-Go' sensor," Anal. Methods, 10, 1579, 2018.

9TH ISAJ ANNUAL SYMPOSIUM-2018

DATE: 07-DEC-2018

AIST TSUKUBA

Special Address

9th Annual Symposium of
INDIAN SCIENTISTS ASSOCIATION IN JAPAN (ISAJ)
Interdisciplinary Science & Technology for Safety and Quality of Life

December 7, 2018 (Friday)
Venue: AIST Auditorium, Tsukuba

Sponsors: EcoCycle Corporation, Ambika

Keynote Lecture

Interaction among participants

Inaugural Address

Participants

EVENT REPORT

9th Annual Symposium of ISAJ

Interdisciplinary Science and Technology for Safety and Quality of Life

Held on

December 7th, 2018

At

National Institute of Advanced Industrial Science & Technology (AIST) Auditorium, Tsukuba Science City

Organized by

Indian Scientists' Association in Japan (ISAJ)

Convener: Dr. Sunil Kaul; Co-conveners: Dr. Manjiri R. Kulkarni, Dr. Priyanka Jood

Summary: The symposium covered a wide spectrum of research fields, such as cognitive science, life sciences, disaster prevention, bio-sensors, and many more. It included a session exclusively for young researchers and students, who presented their work as plenary and invited talks.

The Indian Scientists Association in Japan (ISAJ), organized its 9th annual symposium on the topic of “Interdisciplinary science and technology for safety and quality of life” at the National Institute of Advanced Industrial Science and Technology (AIST) auditorium in Tsukuba Science City on 7th December 2018. The symposium began with an overview of the ISAJ activities in a welcome address by the Chairman, Dr. Sunil Kaul, followed by the inspiring and encouraging addresses from Dr. Katsunori Matsuoka, AIST Vice-President and Director General of Department of Life Science & Biotechnology, AIST, and Mr. Raj Kumar Srivastava, Chargé d'affaires, Embassy of India. Both of them stressed on the need, progress, and global influence of the India-Japan relationship, not only for the progress of science for mutual benefit but also for targeting global issues. The inaugural session was then concluded by a vote of thanks from the Vice Chairman of ISAJ, Dr. Alok Singh who thanked all the participants, members of the organizing committee and sponsors for their support in making this symposium a success.

The symposium showcased the most recent advances in scientific research performed in Japan by Indian scientists and their colleagues. Following the objectives of the symposium, it brought together young researchers from wide-ranging topics of emerging areas of science and technology to present their recent breakthroughs aimed towards the betterment of safety and quality of life. To the benefit of the younger researchers, throughout the day a number of plenary and invited talks were given by very senior scientists about progress in their field of research, such as in biology and medicine, power and structural engineering, energy and environment. A total of 16 talks were given by very senior and young scientists, each of 20 minutes duration. Lively discussions followed each talk. A special session provided the opportunity to 7 selected students to talk about their doctoral research (each for 10 min.). As in every year, a highlight of the symposium was the poster session, providing ample opportunities for young researchers and

students to present their research. There were 44 presentations in the poster session. A high level of discussion and interaction occurred during this session.

Tsukuba science city made an excellent venue for this year’s symposium because the city houses many national research laboratories and a national university. The symposium was attended by about 100 participants from a broad range of disciplines of science and technology. They included prominent scholars, young researchers, and graduate students, coming as far as from Kyoto and Sendai in Japan, and representing academia, industry, and national laboratories. They also represented several nationalities. Some of the young Indian researchers represented laboratory of a 2018 Nobel Laureate in medicine, Prof. Tasuku Honjo (Kyoto University).

The concluding session featured a short presentation on the biomechanics of yoga and presentation of the best poster presentation awards. Dr. Yoshiaki Onishi of AIST, Dr. Sunil Kaul, Dr. Alok Singh, and Dr. Kedar Mahapatra presented four awards to Ms. Manpreet Kaur (NIMS), Ms. Madhu Malinee (Kyoto University), Mr. Vaibhav Mehta (Yokohama International University) and Ms. Jia Wang (AIST).

Poster session and interaction among researchers during 9th annual ISAJ symposium

Indicators of mitochondrial activation in killer T cells could be a biomarker to predict the PD-1 blockade therapeutic efficacy

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Mr. Alok Kumar is a Ph.D. scholar in the 'Department of Immunology and Genomic Medicine, Graduate School of Medicine, Kyoto University' under the supervision of renowned immunologist Prof. Tasuku Honjo (Nobel Prize, Medicine, 2018). He has received a master degree M.Sc. in Biotechnology from IIT Roorkee in 2013.

His research interests include cancer immunotherapy (especially PD-1 blockade based). His research is based on trying to understand the mechanism of unresponsiveness for the rest half population. He is also interested in identification of predictive biomarker to differentiate responder and non-responders for the PD-1 blockade therapy.

Cancer is the leading causes of morbidity and mortality worldwide. Programmed cell death protein 1 (PD-1), an immune-inhibitory receptor expressed on activated T cells, regulates tolerance and autoimmunity [1]. Cancer cells evade the immune response by upregulating the expression of PD-L1 (a ligand of PD-1). Immunotherapy by PD-1 blockade has given revolutionary impact in cancer treatments by its durable effect and high efficacy against a wide variety of cancers with limited side-effects compared to traditional (chemo- and radiation) and other immune therapy [2]. However, around 40-50% of patients still remain unresponsive or less responsive to the PD-1 blockade therapy. Consequently, effort has been focused on identification of biomarkers that can distinguish between responders and non-responders at the initiation of the PD-1 blockade treatment to save precious time of patients, laborious efforts of doctors and cost of social welfare. However, none of the biomarkers (e.g. mutation burden, PD-L1 expression, T cell infiltration to tumor-mass) reported so far have been demonstrated useful in clinical samples. It is known that CD8+ T cells are major effector cells in tumor rejection driven by PD-1 blockade therapy and they are dysfunctional in unresponsive tumors [3]. Recent reports suggest that mitochondrial energy metabolism regulates T cell differentiation. Therefore, we hypothe-

sized that mitochondrial activation parameters could serve as a potential biomarker to differentiate responding and non-responding patients. To test this hypothesis, first we measured oxygen consumption rate (OCR), an indicator of mitochondrial respiration of CD8+ T cells in draining lymph node (DLN) in responsive (MC38, colon carcinoma cell line) and nonresponsive (LLC, lewis lung carcinoma cell line)-tumor-bearing mice from C57BL/6N background treated with anti-PD-1 mAb. We found that OCR was higher in treated responsive group compared to unresponsive group. OCR measurement, being difficult to apply in clinics, it is required to find surrogate biomarker. In order to find surrogate biomarker, we investigated mitochondrial mass, mitochondrial membrane potential and T-bet (a transcription factor associated with T cell killer function) of CD8+ T cells from PBMC (blood). Interestingly, these parameters were also higher in effector T cells of responsive tumor-bearing host compared to unresponsive group. We observed similar results from other genetic background (BALB/c) also. Based on our initial findings in mice we can say that mitochondrial activation parameters will serve as a potential biomarker to differentiate responder and non-responders to the PD-1 blockade therapy. **References:**

- [1] J. Immunol., 2017, 179, p5064-70.
- [2] Int. J. Clin. Onco., 2016, 21, 3, p462-473.
- [3] Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci. USA 2017 114(5): E761-E770.

Fig. Oxygen consumption rate (OCR) of CD8+ T cells purified from draining lymph node of A. MC38 (a responsive tumor)- bearing mice B. LLC (an unresponsive tumor)- bearing mice treated with anti-PD-L1 mAb. Tumor cells were injected on day 0 and mice were treated with anti-PD-L1 mAb on day 5 and day 10 and were sacrificed on day 12. CD8+ T cells were purified from DLN of sacrificed mice from respective group.

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